

Forest disturbances under climate change

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43 **Around the globe forest disturbances are responding to ongoing changes in climate,**
44 **increasingly challenging the sustainable provisioning of ecosystem services. Yet, our**
45 **understanding of disturbance change remains fragmented, as disturbance processes are**
46 **frequently studied independently and at local scales, disregarding interactions and**
47 **large-scale patterns. Here we provide a comprehensive global synthesis of climate**
48 **change effects on important abiotic (fire, drought, wind, snow & ice) and biotic (insects,**
49 **pathogens) disturbance agents. Warmer and drier conditions particularly facilitate fire,**
50 **drought, and insects, while warmer and wetter conditions increase disturbances from**
51 **wind and pathogens. Widespread interactions between agents are likely to amplify**
52 **disturbances, while indirect climate effects such as vegetation changes can dampen long-**
53 **term climate sensitivities. Future disturbance change is likely to be most pronounced in**
54 **coniferous forests and the boreal biome. The emerging disturbance trajectories call for a**
55 **preparation of both ecosystems and society for an increasingly disturbed future of**
56 **forests.**

57

58 Natural disturbances such as fires, insect outbreaks or windthrows are an integral part
59 of ecosystem dynamics in forests around the globe. They occur as relatively discrete events,
60 and form characteristic regimes of typical disturbance frequencies, sizes, and severities over
61 extended spatial and temporal scales^{1,2}. Disturbances disrupt the structure, composition, and
62 function of an ecosystem, community, or population, and change resource availability or the
63 physical environment³. In doing so they create heterogeneity on the landscape⁴, foster
64 diversity across a wide range of guilds and species^{5,6}, and can initiate ecosystem renewal and
65 reorganization^{7,8}.

66 Disturbance regimes have changed profoundly in many forest ecosystems in recent
67 years, with climate being a prominent driver of disturbance change⁹. An increase in

68 disturbance occurrence and severity has been documented over large parts of the globe, e.g.,
69 for fire ^{10,11}, insect outbreaks ^{12,13}, and drought ^{14,15}. Such alterations of disturbance regimes
70 have the potential to strongly impact the ability of forests to provide ecosystem services to
71 society ⁶. Moreover, a climate-mediated increase in disturbances could exceed the ecological
72 resilience of forests, resulting in lastingly altered ecosystems or shifts to non-forest
73 ecosystems as tipping points are crossed ¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Consequently, disturbance change is expected
74 to be among the most profound impacts that climate change will have on forest ecosystems in
75 the coming decades ¹⁹.

76 The ongoing changes in disturbance regimes in combination with their strong and
77 lasting impacts on ecosystems have led to an intensification of disturbance research in recent
78 years. There is a long tradition of disturbance research in ecology ^{3,20,21}, with an increasing
79 focus on understanding the links between disturbance and climate in recent decades ^{1,22,23}.
80 Syntheses on the effects of climate change on important disturbance agents such as fire ²⁴,
81 bark beetles ²⁵, pathogens ²⁶, and drought ¹⁵ summarize recent advances of a highly prolific
82 field of study. Considerably less synthetic knowledge is available on interactions among
83 individual disturbance agents ²⁷⁻²⁹. Furthermore, to date no global synthesis exists that
84 integrates insights on changing disturbance regimes across agents and regions. Yet, the main
85 drivers of disturbance change are global in scale (e.g., climate warming), rendering such a
86 global synthesis highly relevant ^{30,31}.

87 Specifically, a comprehensive analysis of the multiple pathways via which climate
88 might influence forest disturbances is still lacking. Interactions between different disturbance
89 agents can, for instance, result in strong and nonlinear effects of climate change on
90 disturbance activity ³². In contrast, climate-mediated vegetation changes can dampen the
91 climate sensitivity of disturbances ³³. Many assessments of disturbance responses to climate
92 change are currently neglecting such complex effect pathways ^{34,35}. More commonly still, the
93 effects of changing disturbance regimes are disregarded entirely in analyses of future forest

94 development^{36,37} and studies quantifying the climate change mitigation potential of forest
95 ecosystems³⁸, potentially inducing significant bias^{39,40}.

96 Here we review the current understanding of forest disturbances under climate
97 change, focusing on naturally occurring agents of disturbance. Specifically, we synthesize the
98 existing knowledge of how climate change may affect disturbance regimes via direct, indirect,
99 and interaction effects. We reviewed the disturbance literature published after 1989, applying
100 a consistent analysis framework over a diverse set of major forest disturbance agents,
101 including four abiotic (i.e., fire, drought, wind, snow & ice) and two biotic agents (i.e.,
102 insects, pathogens). We compiled evidence for climate effects from all biomes and continents,
103 and analyzed it in a qualitative modeling framework. We tested the hypothesis that climate
104 change will considerably increase forest disturbance activity at the global scale, and
105 specifically that positive, amplifying effects of climate change on disturbances dominate
106 negative, dampening effects.

107

108 **Literature review and analysis**

109 We screened the literature for peer-reviewed English-language papers addressing the climate
110 sensitivity of forest disturbances (i.e., a change in disturbance in response to a change in
111 climate). Due to conceptual advances in disturbance ecology in the 1980s^{3,21} and the
112 increasing availability of climate scenario data and remotely sensed information we chose to
113 focus our analysis on research emerging from the year 1990 onwards. Material was selected
114 by searching for our six focal disturbance agents (i.e., fire, drought, wind, snow & ice, insects,
115 and pathogens) or applicable aliases (e.g., bark beetles or defoliators for the insects category),
116 in combination with the terms climate and/ or climatic change in the title, abstract, and/ or key
117 words of published papers. In the context of drought it is important to note that we here
118 applied an ecological definition rather than a meteorological one, i.e., we focused on events of
119 severe water limitation that affect ecosystem structure and functioning, and thus fall under the

120 definition of ecological disturbance. After initially screening the abstracts of several
121 thousands of papers, studies not directly addressing climatic controls of disturbances (e.g.,
122 work describing disturbance patterns but not their climatic drivers), and those unrelated to the
123 subject matter (e.g., work on insect species that are reproducing in dead trees and are thus not
124 acting as disturbance agent) were excluded, and 674 papers were selected for detailed review.
125 As individual papers frequently contained evidence for more than one climatic effect on
126 disturbances, 1,669 observations were extracted from the selected papers (see Supplementary
127 Text as well as Table S1, and Figure S1-S2 in the Supplementary Information). We conducted
128 an in-depth uncertainty analysis of the information synthesized from the literature, assessing
129 how well the data corresponded with the variable of interest in our analysis (i.e., disturbance
130 activity and changes therein), and evaluating the methodological rigor applied in its
131 generation (see Supplementary Text, Figures S3-S5). We subsequently omitted information
132 that we deemed to be a poor proxy for disturbance change or of limited methodological rigor,
133 resulting in 1,621 observations available for analysis (Supplementary Dataset 1).

134 We applied a common analysis scheme to all reviewed papers. For each paper we
135 recorded meta-data on study location, methodological approach (i.e., empirical, experimental,
136 or simulation-based), and the disturbance agent(s) studied. We distinguished direct, indirect,
137 and interaction effects⁴¹⁻⁴³ of climate change on disturbances in our analysis of the literature.
138 Direct effects were defined as the unmediated impacts of climate variables on disturbance
139 processes. Examples included changes in the frequency or severity of wind events and
140 drought periods, changes in lightning activity, or climate-mediated changes in the metabolic
141 rates of pests and pathogens. Indirect effects were defined as changes in the disturbance
142 regime through climate effects on vegetation and other ecosystem processes not directly
143 related to disturbances. Prominent processes considered here are climate-mediated changes in
144 the tree population and community composition, and include an alteration of the disturbance
145 susceptibility through a change in tree species composition, size, density (e.g., fuel available

146 for burning), and distribution, as well as changes in tree-level vulnerability (e.g., changes in
147 soil anchorage of trees against wind due to variation in soil frost). Interaction effects were
148 defined as linked or compounding relationships between disturbance agents ²⁷, such as an
149 increased risk of bark beetle outbreaks resulting from wind disturbance (creating large
150 amounts of effectively defenseless breeding material supporting the build-up of beetle
151 population) or drought (weakening tree defenses against beetles). Only interactions between
152 the six agents investigated here were considered explicitly.

153 To characterize the climate sensitivity of disturbances we first collated the evidence
154 for direct, indirect, and interaction effects of climate change for each of the six disturbance
155 agents studied. We screened the information for key climatic drivers of disturbances, and
156 analyzed their variation over biomes. As an auxiliary variable we determined the response
157 time of the ecosystem (i.e., the time needed to respond to a respective change in a climate
158 driver) on an ordinal scale. Subsequently, we synthesized the literature regarding potential
159 future changes in the disturbance regime. This analysis was conducted at two levels: First, the
160 sign of the climate effect (i.e., positive: more disturbance, negative: less disturbance) in
161 response to changes in the respective climate variable(s) was assessed. Interaction effects
162 were grouped by directionality (links between individual agents) and also analyzed for the
163 sign of the interaction. This information was synthesized qualitatively, scrutinizing whether
164 amplifying or dampening climate change impacts prevail for each disturbance agent (Figure
165 S6). We conducted this analysis separately for two broad trajectories of change: (1) Warmer
166 and wetter conditions, which assume an increase in both indicators of the thermal
167 environment and water availability (e.g., warmer temperatures, higher levels of precipitation
168 and soil moisture, or lower levels of water deficit and drought indices), and (2) warmer and
169 drier conditions, with an opposite direction of change for indicators of water availability
170 under warming temperatures (see Supplementary Text for details). Second, we calculated a
171 relative effect size (disturbance change in response to future climate change relative to

172 baseline climate conditions, with a value of one indicating no change) across all the potential
173 future climate conditions studied in the literature. Relative effect sizes were tested against the
174 null hypothesis of no change in disturbance as a result of climate change using Wilcoxon
175 signed rank sum tests. All analyses were conducted using the R language and environment for
176 statistical computing ⁴⁴, specifically employing the packages circlize ⁴⁵ and fsmb ⁴⁶.

177

178 **Pathways of climate influence**

179 We found evidence for a substantial influence of climate on disturbances via all three
180 scrutinized pathways, i.e., direct, indirect, and interaction effects. More than half of the
181 observations reported in the literature related to direct climate effects (57.1%), which were the
182 most prominent pathway of climate influence for all analyzed agents except insects (Figure
183 1). Direct effects were found to be particularly pronounced for abiotic agents: Abiotic
184 disturbances often are the direct consequence of climatic extremes, and are thus highly
185 sensitive to changes in their occurrence, intensity, and duration (Table 1). Furthermore, 25.0%
186 of the analyzed observations reported indirect effects of climate change on disturbances.
187 Climate-mediated changes in forest structure and composition were particularly relevant in
188 the context of wind disturbance. Also interactions between disturbance agents are well
189 documented in the analyzed literature (17.9% of the overall observations). For insects, for
190 instance, 40.8% of the reported effects were associated with disturbance interactions. Links
191 between abiotic (influencing agent) to biotic (influenced agent) disturbances were found to be
192 particularly strong (Figure 2a). The large majority of the recorded interaction effects were
193 positive or predominately positive (71.0%), indicating an amplification of disturbance as a
194 result of the interaction between agents. In particular, disturbances by drought and wind
195 strongly facilitate the activity of other disturbance agents, such as insects and fire (Figure 2b,
196 Table S2). Overall, only 16.2% of the studies on disturbance interactions reported a negative
197 or predominately negative (i.e., dampening) effect between interacting disturbance agents.

198

199 **Climate drivers and response times**

200 The climatic drivers of disturbances varied strongly with agent and region. However,
201 temperature-related variables were the most prominent climatic drivers reported in the forest
202 disturbance literature (42.0%). Water availability was a second important climatic influence
203 on disturbance regimes (37.9%). The importance of temperature-related variables on the
204 disturbance regime increased with latitude and was highest in the boreal biome (Figure S9).
205 Conversely, the importance of water availability decreased with latitude and was highest in
206 the tropics. In addition to temperature and water availability, a wide range of other climate-
207 related variables were associated with disturbance change, ranging from wind speed and
208 atmospheric moisture content to snow pack and atmospheric CO₂ concentration.

209 The response times of the disturbance regime to changes in the climate system varied
210 widely, ranging from annual to centennial scales. Response times were clearly related to the
211 type of climate effect, with disturbance interactions constituting the fastest responding
212 pathway and indirect effects being the slowest (Figure S10). For interaction effects, the
213 analyzed literature reports a response time of <6 years in 81.0% of the reviewed cases, and
214 only 9.0% of the studied interaction effects have a response time of >25 years. For indirect
215 effects, only 38.6% of the systems responded within the first five years of the respective
216 climatic forcing, while 44.6% of the responses took >25 years.

217

218 **Potential future disturbance change**

219 At the global scale, our analysis suggests that disturbances from five out of the six analyzed
220 agents are likely to increase in a warming world. The exception are disturbances from snow &
221 ice, which are likely to decrease in the future, especially under warmer and drier conditions
222 (Figure S7, S11). For warmer and dryer future conditions, the large majority of studies
223 suggested an increase in fires (82.4% of the observations), drought (74.2%), and insect

224 activity (78.4%) (Figure 3). Under warmer and wetter conditions, on the other hand, the
225 evidence for increased activity from these disturbance agents was significantly reduced
226 (55.0%, 51.2%, and 65.3%, respectively). Wetter conditions were found to particularly foster
227 wind disturbance (expected to increase in 89.1% of the cases) and pathogen activity (69.0%).
228 Indirect climate effects were dampening the overall climate sensitivity of the system more
229 often than direct climate effects (Table S2, Figures S7-S8), although no significant differences
230 in effect sizes were found (Figure S13). Interaction effects were largely amplifying climate
231 sensitivity (Figure 2).

232 Across all scenarios considered in the analyzed literature, the ratio between
233 disturbances under future climate to disturbances under baseline conditions was significantly
234 positive ($p < 0.05$). The exception were disturbances from snow & ice, which decreased
235 significantly (median effect size of 0.345 over all studies and climate change scenarios, see
236 Figure S11). Disturbances from all other agents increased under future climate change, with
237 median effect sizes of between 1.34 and 1.51. Climate-related disturbance effects were
238 positive across all biomes ($p < 0.001$) and moderately increased with latitude (Figure S12),
239 with the highest values reported for the boreal zone (1.71). Furthermore, coniferous forests
240 had a significantly higher future disturbance effect size than broadleaved and mixed forest
241 types (Figure S14). Also, longer response times of disturbances to climate change were
242 associated with elevated effect sizes (Figure S15).

243

244 **Discussion and conclusion**

245 We found strong support for the hypothesis that climate change could markedly modify future
246 forest disturbance regimes at the global scale. Our analysis of the global forest disturbance
247 literature suggests that particularly disturbances from fire, insects, and pathogens are likely to
248 increase in a warming world (regardless of changes in water availability). These agents and
249 their interactions currently dominate disturbance regimes in many forests of the world, and

250 will likely gain further importance globally in the coming decades. Future changes of
251 disturbances caused by other agents such as drought, wind, and snow will be strongly
252 contingent on changes in water availability, which can be expected to vary more strongly
253 locally and intra-annually than temperature changes. Wind disturbance, for instance, which is
254 currently the most important disturbance agent in Europe ⁴⁰, is expected to respond more
255 strongly to changes in precipitation (and the corresponding changes in tree soil anchorage and
256 tree growth) than to warming temperatures (cf. Figure 3a,b). Yet the most influential climate
257 variable determining wind disturbance remains the frequency and intensity of strong winds,
258 for which current and future trends remain inconclusive ^{47,48}. In general, our global summary
259 of the climate sensitivity of forest disturbance regimes suggests that the recently observed
260 increases in disturbance activity ^{10,40,49} are likely to continue in the coming decades as climate
261 warms further ^{50,51}.

262 Our synthesis of effect pathways showed that direct climate effects were by far the
263 most prominently reported impact in the analyzed literature. This underlines the importance of
264 climatic drivers as inciting factors of tree mortality, and highlights the strong dependence of
265 developmental rates of biotic disturbance agents on climatic conditions ^{26,35}. However, the
266 prominence of direct effects in the literature may at least partially result from the fact that
267 they are easier to study and isolate (e.g., in laboratory experiments ⁵²) than indirect and
268 interaction effects. Publication bias might thus result in an overestimation of the importance
269 of direct effects relative to indirect and interaction effects in our analysis.

270 Indirect effects, mediated by climate-related changes in vegetation structure and
271 composition, were most frequently reported for wind disturbance, but were documented in the
272 literature for all six studied disturbance agents. They are slower than climate effects via direct
273 and interaction pathways, with response times frequently in the range of several decades.
274 Also, indirect effects are often dampening disturbance increases (Table S2, Figures S7-S8),
275 e.g., when trees susceptible to an increasingly aggressive insect pest are outcompeted by

276 individuals or species better adapted to warmer climates, resulting in a system less vulnerable
277 to disturbances^{33,53}. A second important class of dampening indirect effects occur when a
278 previous disturbance event lowers the probability for subsequent disturbances by the same
279 agent, e.g., through a disturbance-induced alteration of forest structure or the depletion of the
280 resource a disturbance agent depends upon⁵⁴⁻⁵⁶. The temporal mismatch observed between
281 direct and indirect effects (Figure S10) suggests that disturbances will likely increase further
282 in the coming decades, as dampening effects of changes in forest structure and composition
283 take effect only with considerable delay. Here it has to be noted that our estimate of response
284 times to climatic changes is necessarily truncated by the observation periods of the underlying
285 studies. It might thus be biased against long-term effects⁸ and underestimate the full temporal
286 extent of climate effects on disturbances.

287 Evidence for potential changes in disturbance interactions was found for all six
288 investigated agents. In this context it is noteworthy that the large majority of the interaction
289 effects reported in the literature are positive, i.e., amplifying disturbance activity. We showed
290 that interactions are especially important for the dynamics of biotic disturbance agents. As an
291 increasing disturbance activity under climate change also means an increasing propensity for
292 disturbance interactions, biotic agents could be particularly⁸ prone to further intensification via
293 the influence of other disturbance agents^{29,57}. This is of growing concern as amplification of
294 disturbances through interactions could also increase the potential for the exceedance of
295 ecological thresholds and tipping points^{27,58}.

296 Particularly indirect and interaction effects of climate change on disturbance regimes
297 need to be better understood to comprehensively assess future trajectories of disturbance in a
298 changing world. The complexity of disturbance interactions complicates predictions of future
299 forest change, and highlights the need for further research comprising multiple interacting
300 disturbance agents and larger spatiotemporal scales. Dynamic vegetation models are prime
301 tools for this domain of inquiry⁵⁹. Simulation models are able to consistently track vegetation

302 – disturbance feedbacks over time frames of decades to centuries^{33,60}, and allow controlled
303 experiments to isolate the effects of interactions between different agents^{32,60}. However,
304 many current disturbance models either do not explicitly consider vegetation processes, or
305 disturbance agents are simulated in isolation, neglecting potential interaction effects. Future
306 work should thus focus on integrating disturbance and vegetation dynamics in models, in
307 order to address the complex interrelations between climate, vegetation, and disturbance^{61,62}.
308 Furthermore, long-term ecological observations and dedicated experimentation are needed to
309 improve our understanding of changing disturbance regimes, and provide the data needed for
310 parameterizing and evaluating the above mentioned simulation models⁵⁹.

311 Our analysis revealed a strong bias of the literature towards agents such as fire,
312 drought, insects, and pathogens, as well as ecosystems located in North America and Europe
313 (Table S1, Figure S1). However, climate change is a global phenomenon, affecting forests in
314 all regions of the world. To obtain a more comprehensive understanding of the global patterns
315 of disturbance change, considerable knowledge gaps on the climate sensitivity of disturbance
316 regimes need to be filled. It remains unclear, for instance, if the increasing effect of future
317 climate change with latitude reported here (Figure S9) is the result of an increased exposure of
318 boreal forests to climate change in combination with naturally lower tree species diversity, or
319 whether it is simply the effect of a publication bias towards these ecosystems. Furthermore,
320 the fact that disturbance research is currently focused on a limited number of agents could be
321 increasingly problematic in the future, as agents that were of little regional relevance in the
322 past could gain importance under changing climatic conditions. In this regard it should be
323 noted that invasive alien pests^{63,64} were not in the focus of our analysis, but are likely to
324 contribute considerably to future changes in disturbance regimes.

325 Climate-induced changes in disturbance regimes are a major challenge for the
326 sustainable provisioning of ecosystem services to society^{6,14}. Our finding of prominent
327 indirect effects suggests that forest management can actively modulate the climate sensitivity

328 of disturbance regimes via modifying forest structure and composition. However, mitigating
329 the direct effects of a changing climate through management will be rarely possible, which
330 suggests that future management will need to find ways of coping with disturbance change. A
331 promising approach in this regard is to foster the resilience of forests to changing disturbance
332 regimes, enabling their recovery from and adaptation to disturbances ^{17,65}, in order to ensure a
333 continuous provisioning of ecosystem services ¹⁸, and ultimately prepare both ecosystems and
334 society for an increasingly disturbed future of forests.

335

336

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353

354 **Author contributions**

355 R. Seidl and C.P.O. Reyer initiated the research. R. Seidl and D. Thom designed the study,
356 with feedback from authors during workshops in Vienna, Austria (April 2015) and Novi Sad,
357 Serbia (November 2015). G. Vacchiano, D. Ascoli, P. Mairota, C.P.O. Reyer, and R. Seidl
358 reviewed the fire literature. D. Martin-Benito, M. Petr, and V. Trotsiuk reviewed the drought
359 literature. J. Wild, M.J. Lexer, M. Fabrika, and T. Nagel reviewed the wind literature. D.
360 Thom and T. Nagel reviewed the snow & ice literature. M. Kautz, D. Thom, M.J. Lexer, M.
361 Svoboda, and J. Wild reviewed the literature on insects. M. Peltoniemi, J. Honkaniemi, and
362 M. Petr reviewed the literature on pathogens. R. Seidl conducted the analyses. All authors
363 contributed to writing and revising the manuscript.

364

365 **Additional information**

366 Supplementary information is available in the online version of the paper.

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- 604

605 **Tables**

606

607 Table 1: Important processes through which climate influences forest disturbances.

Disturbance agent	Direct effects: Climate impact through changes in...	Indirect effects: Climate impact through changes in...	Interaction effects: Climate impact through changes in...
Fire	Fuel moisture ²⁴ Ignition (e.g., lightning activity) Fire spread (e.g., wind speed ⁶⁶)	Fuel availability (e.g., vegetation productivity ⁶⁷) Flammability (e.g., vegetation composition) Fuel continuity (e.g., vegetation structure ⁶⁸)	Fuel availability (e.g., via wind or insect disturbance) Fuel continuity (e.g., avalanche paths as fuel breaks ⁶⁹)
Drought	Occurrence of water limitation Duration of water limitation ⁷⁰ Intensity of water deficit ⁷⁰	Water use and water use efficiency (e.g., tree density and competition) Susceptibility to water deficit (e.g., tree species composition ⁷¹)	Water use and water use efficiency (e.g., insect-related density changes) Susceptibility to water deficit (e.g., fire-mediated changes in forest structure ⁷²)
Wind	Occurrence of strong winds ⁷³ Duration of wind events ⁷⁴ Intensity of wind events (e.g., peak wind speeds) ⁷⁵	Tree anchorage (e.g., soil frost ⁷⁵) Wind exposure (e.g., tree growth ⁷⁶) Wind resistance (e.g., tree species composition ⁵⁴)	Wind exposure (e.g., insect disturbances increases canopy roughness) Soil anchorage (e.g., pathogens decrease rooting stability ⁷⁷) Resistance to stem breakage (e.g., pathogens decrease stability)
Snow & Ice	Snow occurrence ⁷⁸ Snow duration ⁷⁹ Occurrence of freezing rain ⁸⁰	Exposure of forest to snow ⁸¹ Avalanche risk ⁸²	Avalanche risk (e.g., through gap formation by bark beetles ⁸³)

Insects	Agent metabolic rate (e.g., reproduction ³⁵) Agent behavior (e.g., consumption ⁸⁴) Agent survival ⁸⁵	Host distribution and range ⁸⁶ Agent - host synchronization (e.g., budburst ⁸⁷) Host defense (e.g., carbohydrate reserves)	Host presence and abundance ³³ Host resistance and defense (e.g., through changes in drought ⁸⁸)
Pathogens	Agent metabolic rate (e.g., respiration ⁵²) Agent abundance ⁸⁹	Host abundance and diversity ⁹⁰ Host defense ⁹¹	Agent interaction and asynchrony ⁹² Agent dispersal (e.g., through vector insects ⁹³)

609

610 **Figure 1: Distribution of evidence for direct, indirect, and interaction effects of climate**
 611 **change on forest disturbance agents in the reviewed literature.** For every agent, arrow
 612 widths and percentages indicate the relative prominence of the respective effect as expressed
 613 by the number of observations extracted from the analyzed literature supporting it. The central
 614 panel displays the aggregate result over all disturbance agents. Direct effects are unmediated
 615 impacts of climate on disturbance processes, while indirect effects describe a climate
 616 influence on disturbances through effects on vegetation and other ecosystem processes.
 617 Interaction effects refer to the focal agent being influenced by other disturbance agents. Image
 618 credits: Wikimedia Commons.

619 **Figure 2: Interactions between forest disturbance agents.** (a) The sector size in the outer circle indicates the distribution of interactions over
 620 agents, while the flows through the center of the circle illustrate the relative importance of interactions between individual agents (as measured by
 621 the number of observations reporting on the respective interaction). Arrows point from the influencing agent to the agent being influenced by the
 622 interaction. (b) Sign of the interaction effect induced by the influencing agent on the influenced agent. n= Number of observations.

